

Anxiety and Coping Mechanisms of Radiologic Technology Professionals Working Overseas

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the levels of anxiety and coping mechanisms among Filipino Radiologic Technology (RT) professionals working overseas, with the aim of proposing a program to strengthen coping capacity and psychological well-being for future graduates. The respondents comprised 32 RT professionals, including graduates of the University of Perpetual Help System DALTA (UPHSD) Calamba Campus, who were currently employed abroad. Data were collected using a structured survey that measured demographic profile, anxiety levels across cultural adjustment, workload, separation from family, and overall well-being, as well as coping strategies categorized into problem-focused, emotion-focused, and

social/religious coping. Findings revealed that respondents experienced moderate anxiety across all domains, with the highest anxiety observed in cultural adjustment related to fear of being misunderstood and in separation from family due to homesickness. Problem-focused, emotion-focused, and social/religious coping strategies were actively employed, with emotion-focused coping significantly associated with lower anxiety related to workload and overall well-being. Analysis of anxiety levels by demographic profile showed no significant differences, except for civil status in overall well-being. Based on these results, the study proposed the program “*From Campus to Care: Strengthening Coping and Well-Being for RT Graduates Pursuing Work Abroad*”, designed to enhance problem-focused, emotion-focused, and social/religious coping, improve cultural adaptation, and promote psychological resilience among soon-to-graduate RT students.

Keywords: *Anxiety, coping mechanisms, problem-focused coping, emotion-focused coping, social and religious coping, overseas employment, psychological well-being, pre-departure preparation, cultural adjustment.*

INTRODUCTION

Filipino health professionals are recognized worldwide for their competence and dedication, and radiologic technologists form part of this vital workforce. Their migration to different parts of the world reflects both the global demand for skilled imaging professionals and the Philippines’ strong educational preparation in allied health sciences. However, working overseas often exposes these professionals to multiple stressors, including heavy workloads, different cultural and workplace expectations, and systemic

challenges such as discrimination or limited support systems (Al-Btoush & El-Bcheraoui, 2024). These conditions can contribute to significant levels of anxiety that affect both personal well-being and professional performance.

The education and clinical training that graduates receive from the University of Perpetual Help System DALTA Calamba Campus provide them with a solid foundation of theoretical knowledge, technical expertise, and professional values necessary for clinical practice. Their exposure to hospital-based practicums and patient-centered care during their training equips them with competencies to work effectively in diverse healthcare environments. However, while these skills prepare them for technical and clinical demands, they do not fully shield them from the psychological and emotional challenges of adapting to foreign healthcare systems. This suggests a need to examine how well-prepared graduates are in handling stress and what coping mechanisms they adopt once they are employed abroad.

For radiologic technologists specifically, the overseas work environment can heighten psychological strain. They are tasked with ensuring diagnostic accuracy and patient safety in fast-paced clinical settings, while also adapting to advanced imaging technologies and differing professional scopes of practice. Such responsibilities, combined with migration-related stressors like language barriers, isolation, and separation from family, can significantly elevate levels of anxiety (Gransjøen, 2024). Prolonged anxiety not only threatens their health but may also compromise their diagnostic performance and professional longevity.

Research has shown that Filipino migrant healthcare workers experience unique stressors that intensify psychological burden. For example, Filipino nurses in the UK during the COVID-19 pandemic described feelings of “inescapability” and mental strain, reflecting the toll of both professional and cultural challenges (Borbolla & Nkansa-Dwamena, 2025). Similarly, reviews highlight that migrant healthcare professionals face difficulties such as adapting to new healthcare systems, language and communication barriers, and cultural differences that directly impact their mental health (Al-Btoush & El-Bcheraoui, 2024). These findings underscore the importance of examining similar issues among radiologic technologists, a group that remains underrepresented in migration and mental health research.

Coping mechanisms play a crucial role in helping overseas professionals manage their anxiety. Strategies such as prayer, positive reframing, seeking social support, and self-care have been documented as effective among frontline healthcare workers (Rony, Islam, & Alamgir, 2022). Identifying the coping mechanisms used by Filipino radiologic technologists abroad can inform interventions by educational institutions, employers, and policymakers. More importantly, understanding their anxiety experiences provides an opportunity to bridge the gap between academic training and the real-world demands of overseas practice. Thus, this study sought to explore the anxiety levels and coping mechanisms of radiologic technology professionals working overseas, with a particular focus on graduates of UPHSD Calamba Campus, to ensure that their training translates not only into clinical competence but also into resilience and adaptability in the global healthcare arena.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on two psychological theories: Lazarus and Folkman’s Transactional Model of Stress and Coping (1984) and Bandura’s Social Cognitive Theory (1986). Together, these frameworks provide a lens to understand how Filipino radiologic technology professionals experience anxiety in overseas work environments and how they employ coping strategies to manage stress.

Lazarus and Folkman’s model posits that stress is a dynamic process arising from the interaction between the individual and the environment. Anxiety develops when professionals perceive work demands and contextual stressors, such as cultural adjustment, workload, or separation from family, as exceeding their coping resources. Within this framework, two key processes are emphasized: cognitive appraisal or how one evaluates a stressor as threatening or manageable and coping responses or the strategies employed to reduce stress or regulate emotions. Coping is categorized into problem-focused coping, which addresses the stressor directly like learning new clinical protocols, improving language skills, and emotion-focused

coping, which seeks to regulate emotional distress like prayer, social support, positive reframing (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). This model is highly relevant, as migrant radiologic technologists continuously appraise new and often challenging work environments and must adapt their coping responses to sustain psychological well-being.

On the other hand, Bandura’s Social Cognitive Theory emphasizes the role of self-efficacy, belief in one’s capacity to perform tasks effectively, in shaping coping and adaptation. Filipino radiologic technologists who trained at the University of Perpetual Help System DALTA Calamba Campus may enter overseas employment with strong technical competencies and professional identity, which can enhance self-efficacy in clinical practice. However, when confronted with novel systems, cultural differences, or discrimination, their coping effectiveness depends not only on technical skill but also on confidence in their ability to overcome barriers. Self-efficacy influences the choice of coping strategies, persistence in the face of adversity, and resilience against anxiety (Bandura, 1986).

Integrating these two frameworks, the study conceptualizes anxiety among Filipino radiologic technology professionals as a product of the transaction between individual resources and environmental demands in overseas settings. Coping mechanisms are understood as adaptive responses shaped by both cognitive appraisal (Lazarus & Folkman) and self-efficacy beliefs (Bandura). For instance, professionals who appraise cultural adjustment challenges as manageable and believe in their ability to succeed are more likely to adopt problem-focused coping strategies, whereas those overwhelmed by stressors may rely on emotion-focused coping to regulate distress. This dual-theory approach allows for a comprehensive analysis of both the sources of anxiety and the effectiveness of coping mechanisms in supporting resilience and well-being.

By situating the experiences of BS Radiologic Technology graduates including UPHSD’s own graduates within these theoretical frameworks, this study highlighted the importance of not only equipping students with clinical skills but also preparing them with psychosocial competencies that enhance their ability to cope with stress in international work environments. Ultimately, the framework supported the study’s aim to explore how anxiety manifests among Filipino radiologic technology professionals working overseas and what coping mechanisms they employ to sustain professional effectiveness and personal well-being.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. *Conceptual Paradigm*

Figure 1 shows that workplace demands such as workload, time pressure, communication barriers, and cultural adjustment can lead to psychological strain and anxiety if not balanced by sufficient job and personal resources. In this context, coping mechanisms act as personal resources that help mitigate the negative effects of job demands. In the present study, job demands referred to the challenges Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals experience while working overseas such as cultural adjustment, workload, separation from family, and overall well-being, that increased their levels of anxiety. Meanwhile, coping mechanisms represented the strategies these professionals employed to manage stress and maintained psychological balance, such as problem-focused coping, social support, and religious or emotion-focused coping.

The conceptual framework assumed that high job demands contributed to increased anxiety, while the presence of effective coping mechanisms helped reduce anxiety and promote better psychological adjustment. Moreover, the strong clinical and academic foundation provided by the school during their college days served as an underlying resource that may enhance coping self-efficacy among its graduates, equipping them to manage the pressures of overseas practice.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to examine the anxiety levels and coping mechanisms of Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas. The following were the specific questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 civil status;
 - 1.4 years of service overseas; and
 - 1.5 country of current employment?
2. What is the level of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas in terms of:
 - 2.1 cultural adjustment;
 - 2.2 workload;
 - 2.3 separation from family; and
 - 2.4 overall well-being?
3. What coping mechanisms do these professionals employ in managing anxiety, particularly in terms of:
 - 3.1 problem-focused;
 - 3.2 emotion-focused; and
 - 3.3 social and religious coping?
4. Is there a significant difference in the levels of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas when grouped according to their profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the levels of anxiety and the coping mechanisms employed by Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas?
6. What program can be proposed by the College of Radiologic Technology among Radiologic Technology graduates to strengthen the coping capacity and psychological well-being after graduation and wish to work abroad?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant differences in the levels of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas when grouped according to their profile.
2. There is no significant relationship between the levels of anxiety and the coping mechanisms employed by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study focused on examining the anxiety levels and coping mechanisms of Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas, including graduates of the University of Perpetual Help System DALTA (UPHSD) Calamba Campus. It aimed to determine the respondents' demographic profile in terms of age, sex, civil status, years of service overseas, and country of current employment, and to assess their level of anxiety in relation to cultural adjustment, workload, separation from family, and overall well-being. Furthermore, the study sought to identify the coping mechanisms they employ, specifically in the aspects of problem-focused coping, emotion-focused coping, and social and religious coping.

The study also determined whether there were significant differences in the levels of anxiety when the respondents are grouped according to their profile, and whether a significant relationship exists between the level of anxiety and the coping mechanisms used. Based on the findings, a proposed program was formulated to strengthen the coping capacity and psychological well-being of UPHSD Calamba Radiologic Technology graduates who aspired to work abroad.

The study was quantitative in nature, utilizing a descriptive-correlational research design that analyzed and interpreted data collected through a survey questionnaire distributed online among Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals currently employed in various countries.

The study was delimited to assessing anxiety and coping mechanisms only. It does not explore other psychological variables such as depression, burnout, or job satisfaction. Moreover, the study did not cover radiologic technologists working locally in the Philippines or those employed in non-clinical settings.

Significance of the Study

This study was significant because it highlighted the psychological well-being and coping strategies of Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas, a group that has not been widely studied compared to nurses and physicians. Understanding these experiences is essential, as unmanaged anxiety can negatively affect both personal well-being and professional performance.

University of Perpetual Help System DALTA Calamba Campus. The findings will be valuable as they will provide feedback on how well the school's academic and clinical training equips graduates for global healthcare practice. Results may guide curriculum enhancement, skills training, and support programs that prepare future graduates not only with technical competencies but also with resilience and adaptive coping skills.

Radiologic Technology Professionals. The study can serve as a source of awareness about potential stressors they may encounter and the coping strategies that can help them adjust successfully. It can also empower professionals to value mental health care alongside professional growth.

Employers and Healthcare Institutions Overseas. The study offers insights into the importance of providing workplace resources and psychosocial support to migrant radiologic technologists. By recognizing the role of organizational support in reducing anxiety, institutions can foster healthier work environments, which in turn improve job satisfaction and patient care quality.

Future Researchers. This study serves as a foundation for exploring the psychological well-being of radiologic technology professionals, a topic that has received limited scholarly attention. By documenting the experiences of Filipino radiologic technologists working overseas, this research can provide baseline data and highlight gaps that may be addressed in future investigations.

Definition of Terms

To provide clarity and uniform understanding, the following terms were defined as they are used in this study:

Anxiety. Operationally, in this study, anxiety refers to the psychological strain experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas due to stressors such as workload, cultural adjustment, and separation from family.

Coping Mechanisms. In this study, coping mechanisms refer to the specific strategies such as problem-focused coping, emotion-focused coping, and seeking social support, employed by Filipino radiologic technologists abroad to handle work- and migration-related stress.

Cultural Adjustment. In this study, it is measured through indicators such as comfort in interacting with foreign colleagues, ability to understand local work practices, and ease of adapting to new social and professional environments.

Emotion-Focused Coping. It pertains to coping strategies aimed at managing emotional responses rather than solving the stressor itself. It includes activities such as relaxation, acceptance, seeking emotional comfort, and engaging in leisure activities to reduce anxiety and emotional tension.

Job Demands. Job demands refer to the workload, role expectations, and external stressors encountered by radiologic technologists in overseas healthcare settings.

Overall Well-being. It encompasses the general psychological, emotional, and physical state of Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working abroad. It includes satisfaction with life, perceived stress levels, and self-assessed mental health status. It is measured through self-reported indicators of happiness, motivation, and life balance.

Problem-Focused Coping. It refers to the coping strategies used by individuals to directly address or solve the source of stress or anxiety. In this study, it includes behaviors such as seeking information, planning, taking action to manage work stress, or finding ways to adapt to new job environments.

Separation from Family. It refers to the emotional and psychological impact experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals due to physical distance from family members in the Philippines. It is measured through the frequency of homesickness, emotional distress, and perceived lack of social and emotional support while working overseas.

Social and Religious Coping. It refers to the coping mechanisms that involve seeking support from others or drawing strength from faith and spiritual practices. This includes communicating with family and friends for encouragement, participating in religious activities, and using prayer or faith as a source of comfort and resilience in facing work-related and personal challenges abroad.

Workload. It pertains to the amount and intensity of professional duties performed by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals abroad, including patient handling, imaging procedures, administrative tasks, and shift schedules. It is operationally measured by the respondents' perceived pressure, time demands, and balance between work responsibilities and rest.

Literature Review

Anxiety Experienced By Filipino Radiologic Technology Professionals Working Overseas

Health workforce migration puts Filipino healthcare professionals in new clinical, social, and regulatory environments. These changes increase exposure to job demands that can create anxiety if not supported by sufficient resources, such as job resources and coping strategies. The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) perspective, recently adapted and used in healthcare research, explains how high job demands, like workload, role ambiguity, and acculturative stress, raise strain. In contrast, job and personal resources, including training, social support, and self-efficacy, help reduce this strain. Research in health settings supports the relevance of the JD-R perspective for migrant clinicians (Yousef, et al. 2024).

Radiology and imaging professionals experience specific stressors that increase their risk of anxiety and burnout. A systematic review of radiological staff found high levels of stress and burnout. It concluded that both individual approaches, like mindfulness and resilience, and organizational strategies are effective. The best outcomes come from combining these methods: using mindfulness and resilience at the individual level and structural or system interventions at the organizational level. This shows that radiologic technologists working abroad, who deal with both job-related and migration challenges, are at greater risk for anxiety and need support at multiple levels (Gransjoen, 2024).

Numerous pandemic-era studies demonstrated that migrant and frontline healthcare workers experienced greater psychological burden; qualitative work among Filipino nurses in the UK documented intense mental strain during COVID-19 and described culturally specific coping strategies and institutional shortcomings that amplified distress. Although these studies focus on nurses, their findings about migration-related anxiety, discrimination, and the buffering effect of social/organizational supports are instructive for allied health professionals such as radiologic technologists who work in similar clinical contexts abroad (Borbolla, 2025).

Local Philippine literature provides direct, context-sensitive evidence about stress and coping among radiologic technology students and recent graduates. A descriptive-correlational study of BS Radiologic Technology students at Universidad de Zamboanga reported generally high psychosocial well-being but also frequent academic problems; students commonly used coping strategies and the study emphasized the need to strengthen coping skills through curricular or support interventions (Dumpac, 2022). A 2024 undergraduate qualitative thesis investigating challenges faced during clinical internship (Trinity University of Asia) identified heavy workload, communication difficulties, inadequate supervision, and the theory-practice gap as key stressors and described common coping techniques used by students (time management, peer support, positive self-talk), suggesting that these early experiences shape later professional coping. Several other institutional studies and theses across Philippine colleges echo similar themes—clinical practicum stress, need for better mentorship, and the value of simulation and preparatory training to reduce anxiety before entering professional practice.

Evidence about coping strategies and coping self-efficacy is also robust and relevant. Reviews and empirical studies show that adaptive coping (problem-focused coping, planning, social support, acceptance) and higher coping self-efficacy are associated with lower anxiety and better psychological outcomes in healthcare workers, while maladaptive coping (avoidance, denial, substance use) predicts worse outcomes. Occupational coping self-efficacy, in particular, has been linked to lower burnout, greater resilience, and reduced turnover in clinical populations—findings that point to self-efficacy as an important target for educational and workplace interventions for migrant radiologic technologists (Wu, 2024).

The role of formal education and clinical training as protective resources has been highlighted across both local and international studies. Philippine institutions including UPHSD Calamba emphasize hands-on clinical practicum and skills training that produce technical competence and professional identity—resources that increase self-confidence when graduates transition to overseas practice. However, local studies also show a gap between what is taught in school and the psychosocial realities of clinical work, suggesting that curricula should include more deliberate training on stress management, communication in diverse settings, and resilience-building to better prepare graduates for international employment.

Level of Anxiety among Healthcare Professionals

Anxiety among healthcare professionals is often classified as mild, moderate, or severe, depending on its intensity and impact on daily functioning. In radiology-related professions, recent reviews indicate that stress and anxiety levels are widespread and variable. Gransjøen (2024) noted that radiological personnel across different countries experience significant psychological strain, with burnout prevalence ranging from 20% to more than 50%, depending on workload and workplace conditions. These levels suggest that many radiologic professionals operate under at least moderate levels of anxiety, which can impair performance and job satisfaction.

Among migrant healthcare workers, the level of anxiety tends to be higher compared to their locally employed counterparts due to acculturative stress, communication barriers, discrimination, and family separation. Borbolla and Nkansa-Dwamena (2025) reported that Filipino nurses in the UK experienced persistent anxiety during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, often describing feelings of being overwhelmed and unsupported. Although this evidence focuses on nurses, it strongly parallels the

experiences of radiologic technologists, who face comparable migration-related challenges in addition to the technical demands of their work.

Local studies of radiologic technology students and interns show that anxiety is already present during the academic and practicum stages. Dumpac (2022) found that RT students at Universidad de Zamboanga experienced moderate levels of anxiety linked to academic pressures, while Cañete et al. (2024) highlighted that during hospital internship, students encountered stressors such as heavy workload and inadequate supervision that contributed to heightened anxiety. These findings imply that even before going overseas, radiologic technologists are vulnerable to moderate to high anxiety levels, which may escalate once they enter unfamiliar international healthcare systems.

Studies measuring anxiety using validated tools such as the Generalized Anxiety Disorder scale (GAD-7) and the Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale (DASS-21) confirm high rates of moderate to severe anxiety among healthcare workers. For example, Al-Shamrani et al. (2024) found that radiology practitioners exhibited notable levels of generalized anxiety disorder following the pandemic, with up to 30% reporting moderate to severe symptoms. These data suggest that radiologic technologists abroad are at risk of experiencing anxiety beyond mild or situational levels, warranting structured support systems.

the level of anxiety among Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas is likely to range from moderate to severe, shaped by both profession-specific demands (workload, patient care stress, technological complexity) and migration-related challenges (acculturation, family separation, communication barriers). Without effective coping mechanisms and institutional support, elevated anxiety can persist, potentially leading to burnout and reduced quality of healthcare delivery. This highlights the importance of assessing anxiety levels systematically and identifying coping strategies that sustain resilience and professional performance.

Coping Mechanisms Do These Professionals Employ In Managing Anxiety

Healthcare workers typically use a mix of problem-focused and emotion-focused coping strategies when facing work stress and anxiety. Problem-focused strategies aim to change or control the stressor (e.g., seeking more information, planning, task re-organization, acquiring new skills), while emotion-focused strategies aim to regulate the emotional response like acceptance, positive reframing, relaxation. Reviews of coping among frontline HCWs during the COVID-19 pandemic consistently report both types in active use; problem-focused coping (planning, problem-solving) is often linked with better adjustment, whereas certain emotion-focused strategies such as acceptance, positive reframing also protect mental health when stressors are uncontrollable (Rony, 2022).

Social support from family, friends, faith communities, and coworkers is one of the most common and effective ways to cope, especially in collectivist cultures like the Philippines. Research on Filipino healthcare workers and other healthcare worker groups shows that seeking family support, both emotional and practical, relying on peer networks at work, and engaging in religious or spiritual practices like prayer and faith groups are typical and meaningful methods for reducing anxiety and improving coping ability. Family support and religious coping were often noted as important protective strategies for Filipino nurses and other health staff working internationally.

Several studies and reviews highlight the importance of coping self-efficacy, which is the belief in one's ability to handle stressful situations. This belief plays a crucial role in affecting outcomes. Higher coping self-efficacy is linked to more frequent use of adaptive, problem-focused strategies, less anxiety, and reduced presenteeism and burnout. Recent research involving ICU and frontline nurses shows that coping self-efficacy helps explain the connection between acute stressors and symptoms of depression or anxiety. This suggests that programs aimed at boosting self-efficacy, such as skills training, mastery experiences, and mentoring, can help lower psychological distress (Wu, 2024).

Occupation- and context-specific coping: Radiology personnel and allied health staff use several practical, job-focused coping behaviors, such as time management, task prioritization, seeking technical training, and peer consultation. These strategies help them manage role overload and technical uncertainty.

Reviews focused on radiology staff show that system-level changes, like workflow redesign and staffing adjustments, along with individual strategies, such as mindfulness, brief on-the-job debriefing, and peer support, together lead to the greatest reductions in stress and anxiety. Considering radiology's high cognitive load and time pressure, problem-focused coping, including clarifying protocols and asking for help, is especially helpful for reducing performance anxiety (Granjoen, 2024).

Maladaptive coping and risks. Not all coping methods reduce anxiety. Avoidance, denial, behavioral disengagement, and substance use are linked to worse outcomes, higher anxiety, and later burnout in some healthcare worker samples. Evidence from the pandemic showed that when organizational or social support was lacking, some professionals relied on maladaptive strategies. This increased their risk for ongoing psychological problems. This highlights the need for early detection and supportive help instead of leaving coping entirely to individuals.

Organizational and system supports matter. Multiple studies show that workplace resources, such as clear communication, routine debriefings, accessible mental health services, mentorship, and adequate staffing and equipment, significantly improve adaptive coping and lower anxiety. In many settings, organizational interventions, like onboarding or orientation for migrants, peer mentoring, and access to counseling, were found to boost coping self-efficacy and reduce distress more than individual interventions on their own. Therefore, coping is best supported by a mix of individual and organizational efforts (Iddrisu, 2023).

Studies and theses from Philippine schools of radiologic technology show that students and early-career RTs often rely on problem-solving, such as time management and simulation practice, peer support, and religious coping to handle stress during their academic and practicum experiences. However, they also note that there are gaps in formal training on psychosocial skills and resilience. Local findings indicate that students develop coping patterns influenced by their culture, including family reliance, prayer, and positive thinking. These strategies likely continue into their professional lives abroad, but the effectiveness of these methods under international work pressures has not been measured for radiologic technologists. This local evidence supports the current study's goal of exploring which coping strategies UPHSD Calamba graduates use overseas and how effective those strategies are at reducing anxiety.

Synthesis

The literature consistently shows that migration puts Filipino healthcare professionals in new clinical, social, and regulatory environments that increase job demands, such as workload, role ambiguity, and acculturative stress. This, in turn, raises the risk of anxiety unless there are adequate job and personal resources to buffer it (Yousef et al., 2024). Radiology and imaging staff face specific pressures, including high caseloads, rapid technology changes, and time constraints. These factors heighten baseline vulnerability to stress and burnout. Systematic reviews indicate that a combination of individual methods, like mindfulness and resilience training, along with organizational support, leads to the best outcomes for reducing this strain (Gransjøen, 2024). Research from the pandemic era shows that migrant and frontline healthcare workers faced significant psychological burdens. Filipino nurses in the UK reported ongoing anxiety worsened by gaps in institutional support. These findings can apply, in principle, to allied health workers such as radiologic technologists who operate in similar high-pressure, cross-cultural environments (Borbolla, 2025).

Philippine studies support this global evidence by showing that anxiety and stress emerge early in training and clinical practice. Descriptive and qualitative research involving BS Radiologic Technology students and interns shows moderate levels of anxiety linked to academic pressure, heavy workloads in practicums, communication challenges, and gaps in supervision (Dumpac, 2022; Cañete et al., 2024). These findings indicate that many radiologic technologists start their professional careers using coping strategies such as time management, peer support, and faith-based approaches. These strategies may influence, but not necessarily stop, later anxiety when they move to roles abroad.

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The literature review supports the need to study anxiety and coping among Filipino radiologic technology professionals working abroad. It also highlights the important role of formal training. While both international and local studies discuss how demands and resources affect coping, there is a noticeable lack of research. Few studies look at how training from Philippine universities, like the clinical preparation at UPHSD Calamba, affects coping self-efficacy, coping strategies, and anxiety levels among radiologic technologists overseas. Filling this gap will help develop better educational programs and workplace support. This can boost resilience and protect the well-being of practitioners, along with the quality of patient care.

METHODS

Research design

This study utilized a quantitative, descriptive- correlational research design to determine the level of anxiety and coping mechanisms of Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas. A quantitative approach was most appropriate because it allowed the collection of measurable data using standardized instruments and facilitates statistical analysis to describe trends, patterns, and relationships within the target population.

The descriptive design was employed to systematically present the current state of anxiety experienced by the respondents and to identify the coping strategies they commonly used in their overseas work contexts. This approach did not attempt to manipulate variables but rather aimed to describe and quantify the phenomenon as it exists among the respondents. The study involved Filipino Radiologic Technology graduates who are currently working abroad, including graduates from the University of Perpetual Help System DALTA (UPHSD) Calamba Campus.

Population and Sampling

The population of this study consists of Radiologic Technology professionals graduated from different universities including those from the University of Perpetual Help System DALTA (UPHSD) Calamba Campus who are currently employed overseas and willingly responded to the survey sent to them.

Because there were only few number of graduates from the College of Radiologic Technology working abroad, and so researchers considered the help of those who are already abroad, for their invitation to join and through the help of friends who have access with other Radiologic Technologists working overseas. Also, the researchers made considered the purposive and network sampling, relying on available contacts and referrals because of limited contacts with the respondents considering that they were the hard to get population due to geographical dispersion and limited access to this group.

Respondent of the study

The respondents of this study were the 32 Radiologic Technology professionals who are currently employed overseas including graduates of the University of Perpetual Help System DALTA (UPHSD) Calamba Campus.

Instrument of the study

The study made use of a standardized survey questionnaire. It was composed of three parts. Part one was about the demographic profile of the respondents such as age, sex, civil status, years of service overseas, and country of current employment. Part two were questions about the level of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas in terms of cultural adjustment, workload, separation from family and overall well-being: Questions were answered using the given scale below:

Scale	Interpretation
5	Always/Very high
4	Often/High
3	Sometimes/Moderate
2	Rarely/Low
1	Never/Very low

Additionally, part three was about coping mechanism in terms of problem-focused, emotion-focused, and social and religious coping. Questions were answered using the given scale below:

Scale	Interpretation
5	Strongly Agree
4	Agree
3	Neutral
2	Disagree
1	Strongly Disagree

Validation of the Instrument

The researchers considered adapting from standardized or validated scales that have demonstrated acceptable reliability, measured through Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranging from 0.70 to 0.95, indicating good to excellent internal consistency. Questions on the level of anxiety was patterned from the Sociocultural Adaptation Scale (SCAS) and Cultural Adjustment Difficulties Scale. These instruments have reported Cronbach's alpha values between 0.80 and 0.91, demonstrating high reliability (Ward & Kennedy, 2020; Lin, Chen, & Song, 2021) and from the Job Stress Scale and the Job Demand-Resources (JD-R) model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017), with prior studies reporting Cronbach's alpha values from 0.82 to 0.90 (Crawford et al., 2020). Additionally, questions on separation from family and over-all well-being were taken from Family Separation Stress Scale and Uchino's (2006) concept of social support and well-being, with Cronbach's alpha reliability between 0.83 and 0.88 (Alonso & Moscoso, 2020; Kim & Kim, 2021) and from Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7 (GAD-7) and WHO-5 Well-Being Index, both of which have Cronbach's alpha values of 0.85 to 0.92 (Spitzer et al., 2006; Topp et al., 2015; De Guzman & Chua, 2021).

Moreover, the coping mechanism questionnaire was adapted from widely used and validated scales, demonstrating high internal consistency with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from 0.70 to 0.95, indicating reliability for research use: Ways of Coping Questionnaire (WCQ) by Lazarus and Folkman (1984) demonstrated Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients between 0.78 and 0.90; Brief COPE and Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) by Gross and John (2003) with Cronbach's alpha values range from 0.75 to 0.89; the Brief RCOPE (Pargament et al., 2011) and social support subscales of the COPE Inventory, with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from 0.82 to 0.94.

Data Gathering Procedures

This study sought the necessary permission and approval to conduct the research. Once approved, the researcher reached out to the university alumni office and the College of Radiologic Technology. The

researcher used the list of graduates whom they know working overseas. These selected respondents were contacted through authorized channels such as social media, phone, or email, and they were given information about the objective, significance, and ethical considerations of the study, including voluntary participation and confidentiality. Additionally, the researchers sought the help of the program chair of the College of Radiologic Technology for possible and additional respondents whom he has contact with for additional respondents of the study. Before any data was collected, the informed consent from all respondents were gathered. Depending on participant accessibility and preference, the primary collection instrument a standardized self-administered questionnaire was distributed electronically through online platforms. The questionnaire gathered data on the graduates' coping mechanisms, anxiety levels, and demographic profiles. To maximize response rates, the data collection period was scheduled over several weeks, with appropriate follow-up reminders. To protect the rights and welfare of the respondents, ethical standards such as confidentiality, anonymity, and the right to withdraw from participation at any time without penalty was strictly observed throughout the process

Statistical Treatment of the Study

The following statistical tools were used to analyze and interpret the quantitative data gathered from the survey:

Frequency and Percentage Distribution. This was used to assess the demographic variables of healthcare personnel such as sex, age, civil status, years of service overseas, and country of current employment.

Mean. This was used to assess the level of anxiety and coping mechanism of graduates radiologic technology working abroad.

T-test and Analysis of Variance. This test were used to determine the significant differences of the respondents in the levels of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas when grouped according to their profile

Pearson Coefficient of Correlation. This was used to determine the a significant relationship between the levels of anxiety and the coping mechanisms employed by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas.

Ethical Consideration

This study considered ethical research guidelines throughout this execution. An informed consent letter outlining the study's title, goal, voluntary nature, and confidentiality guarantee were given to participants prior to their involvement. In accordance with Republic Act 10173, generally known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, a Data Privacy Agreement was also included. The data gathering method only included those who selected "YES" to indicate their consent. All responses were handled with absolute confidentiality, and no personally identifiable information will be collected. Only the researchers working on the project have access to this data. Under the academic supervision of the University of Perpetual Help System DALTA – Calamba Campus, ethical guidelines were followed, guaranteeing that the research complies with both legal and institutional ethical principles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 -5 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, number of years working overseas, and the country where they are currently working.

Table 1. *Frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of age*

Age	Frequency	Percent
21 – 30 years old	23	71.9
31 – 40 years old	9	28.1
Total	32	100.0

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents based on age. A majority of the respondents, 23 out of 32 (71.9%), are between 21 and 30 years old, indicating that most overseas RT professionals are relatively young, likely early in their professional careers. Meanwhile, nine (9) respondents (28.1%) are between 31 and 40 years old, representing mid-career professionals. This age distribution suggests that the overseas Radiologic Technology workforce is predominantly young adults, who may be more flexible and adaptable to working in new environments abroad. Younger professionals might face higher levels of acculturative stress and challenges in coping due to limited prior international experience.

Table 2. *Frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of sex*

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	12	37.5
Female	20	62.5
Total	32	100.0

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents based on sex. Of the 32 Radiologic Technology professionals who participated in the study, the majority were female, with 20 respondents (62.5%), while 12 respondents (37.5%) were male. These results indicate a higher representation of female professionals among Radiologic Technologists working overseas, reflecting the gender distribution within the sample population. This pattern reflects the general trend in allied health professions, where females often comprise a larger proportion of the workforce. The higher number of female respondents may also influence aspects of the study, such as coping strategies and experiences of workplace anxiety.

Table 3. *Frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of civil status*

Civil Status	Frequency	Percent
Single	22	68.8
Married	9	28.1
Separated	1	3.1
Total	32	100.0

Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to civil status. Among the 32 Radiologic Technology professionals surveyed, the majority were single, with 22 respondents (68.8%), followed by 9 married respondents (28.1%), and only 1 respondent (3.1%) who was separated. These results indicate that most of the participants are single, which may reflect the demographic profile of Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas within this sample. This may reflect a common trend in overseas health workforce migration, where younger and unmarried professionals are more likely to pursue employment abroad due to fewer family obligations and greater flexibility in relocation. Being single may also influence their experiences of separation from family, cultural adjustment, and coping mechanisms while working overseas, as they may have fewer immediate domestic responsibilities but potentially greater social or emotional needs for support.

Table 4. *Frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of number of years working overseas*

No. of years	Frequency	Percent
Below one year	1	3.1
1 – 3 years	17	53.1
4 – 6 years	6	18.8
7 – 9 years	6	18.8
10 – above years	2	6.3
Total	32	100.0

Table 4 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents based on their number of years working overseas. The majority of respondents have been working abroad for 1–3 years, with 17 respondents (53.1%), indicating that most participants are relatively early in their international careers. Those with 4–6 years and 7–9 years of overseas experience each comprise 6 respondents (18.8%), while only 2 respondents (6.3%) have worked abroad for 10 years or more, and 1 respondent (3.1%) has been overseas for less than one year. These results suggest that while a few participants are long-term overseas professionals, most are still in the early stages of adapting to international work environments. This early-career exposure may contribute to higher levels of adjustment-related anxiety, requiring them to rely heavily on coping mechanisms such as building peer support networks, learning new workplace systems, and developing resilience to manage the challenges of working abroad.

Table 5. *Frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of country where they currently working*

No. of years	Frequency	Percent
Middle East	6	18.7
United Kingdom	17	53.1
Canada	4	12.5
New Zealand	1	3.1
Australia	1	3.1
Cambodia	1	3.1
Bahamas	1	3.1
Hongkong	1	3.1
Total	32	100.0

Table 5 shows the distribution of respondents according to the country where they are currently employed. The majority of respondents work in the United Kingdom, with 17 participants (53.1%), followed by those working in the Middle East (6 respondents, 18.7%). Smaller numbers of respondents are employed in Canada (4 respondents, 12.5%), New Zealand, Australia, Cambodia, Bahamas, and Hong Kong (1 respondent each, 3.1%). This distribution indicates that a large portion of the participants are concentrated in a few countries, particularly the United Kingdom, which may influence the type of professional challenges, cultural adjustments, and social support systems they experience. Working in diverse international settings can contribute to work-related anxiety, especially when adapting to different healthcare systems, workplace expectations, and cultural norms. At the same time, exposure to multiple countries may foster the development of coping strategies, such as resilience, cultural adaptability, and reliance on expatriate networks, enabling Radiologic Technology professionals to effectively manage stress while working abroad.

Level of Anxiety Experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology Professionals Working Overseas

Table 7. *Level of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas – Cultural Adjustment*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
I feel nervous or anxious when I cannot express myself clearly in the local language.	3.00	Moderate
I worry about being misunderstood or judged by foreign colleagues or supervisors.	3.13	Moderate
I feel uneasy adjusting to different workplace norms or cultural practices.	2.91	Moderate
I feel anxious when dealing with patients or coworkers from cultures different from my own.	2.66	Moderate
I feel stressed when cultural misunderstandings affect my work relation	2.84	Moderate
Composite Mean	2.91	Moderate

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50, Very high; 4.49 - 3.50, High; 3.49 – 2.50, Moderate; 2.49 – 1.50, Low; 1.49 – 1.00, Very Low

Table 7 presents the level of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas in terms of cultural adjustment. The composite mean of 2.91 indicates that, overall, respondents experience a moderate level of anxiety related to adapting to foreign cultural and workplace environments. The highest mean was reported for the indicator “*I worry about being misunderstood or judged by foreign colleagues or supervisors*” (3.13, Moderate), suggesting that concerns about social evaluation and professional acceptance are the most prominent sources of anxiety for these professionals. The lowest mean was noted for “*I feel anxious when dealing with patients or coworkers from cultures different from my own*” (2.66, Moderate), indicating that direct interactions with culturally diverse patients and colleagues, while still a source of stress, are slightly less anxiety-inducing than the fear of judgment or misunderstanding.

These findings can be interpreted using Bandura’s Social Cognitive Theory, which emphasizes the interaction of personal, behavioral, and environmental factors in shaping human experiences. The Radiologic Technologists’ anxiety reflects how environmental challenges abroad such as unfamiliar workplace norms and cultural differences, interact with their personal beliefs and coping behaviors. Additionally, Lazarus and Folkman’s Transactional Model of Stress and Coping provides a framework for understanding how these professionals appraise and respond to stressors. The moderate levels of anxiety suggest that respondents perceive cultural adjustment challenges as stressful but employ coping strategies, such as seeking social support, practicing resilience, and learning adaptive behaviors, to manage their strain.

These interpretations are supported by literature on health workforce migration, which documents that Filipino healthcare professionals face multiple stressors in international settings, including new clinical, social, and regulatory environments (Yousef et al., 2024). Radiology and imaging professionals are particularly vulnerable to stress and burnout due to technical job demands combined with migration-related challenges, and studies show that interventions at both individual (e.g., mindfulness, resilience) and organizational levels are effective in reducing anxiety (Gransjoen, 2024).

Table 8. *Level of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas – Workload*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
I feel anxious when I have too many imaging procedures or patients to handle in a day.	2.50	Moderate
I worry that I might make mistakes because of the heavy workload.	2.75	Moderate
I feel tense or restless when I am asked to work overtime or double shifts.	2.25	Moderate
I feel overwhelmed by the expectations and responsibilities of my job.	2.59	Moderate
I feel anxious when I have to learn or adapt to new imaging technologies or procedures quickly.	2.53	Moderate

Composite Mean	2.53	Moderate
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Legend: 5.00 – 4.50, Very high; 4.49 - 3.50, High; 3.49 – 2.50, Moderate; 2.49 – 1.50, Low; 1.49 – 1.00, Very Low

Table 8 presents the level of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas in terms of workload. The composite mean of 2.53 indicates that respondents experience a moderate level of anxiety related to workload demands. The highest mean was reported for “*I worry that I might make mistakes because of the heavy workload*” (2.75, Moderate), suggesting that concerns about performance accuracy under high work demands are the most significant source of anxiety.

The lowest mean was observed for “*I feel tense or restless when I am asked to work overtime or double shifts*” (2.25, Moderate), indicating that while overtime contributes to stress, it is slightly less anxiety-inducing compared to concerns over errors and responsibilities.

Likewise, these findings can be interpreted through Bandura’s Social Cognitive Theory, which emphasizes the interaction of personal, behavioral, and environmental factors in shaping experiences. The RadTechs’ anxiety reflects how environmental job demands abroad, such as heavy caseloads, overtime, and the need to adapt to new technologies, interact with personal beliefs, confidence in their abilities, and coping behaviors. Additionally, Lazarus and Folkman’s Transactional Model of Stress and Coping explains that these professionals evaluate workload challenges as potentially stressful and respond with coping strategies, such as time management, seeking peer support, or developing resilience.

The results align with literature on health workforce migration, which highlights that Filipino healthcare professionals face elevated stress and anxiety in new clinical, social, and regulatory environments, particularly when job demands exceed available resources (Yousef et al., 2024). Radiology and imaging professionals are specifically vulnerable to stress and burnout due to technical and workload-related pressures, and studies recommend combining individual coping strategies, such as mindfulness and resilience, with organizational support interventions to effectively manage anxiety (Gransjoen, 2024). Local Philippine studies also support these findings: BS Radiologic Technology students and recent graduates report workload-related stress and utilize coping strategies such as time management, peer support, and positive self-talk to manage anxiety, highlighting the continuity of stress and coping patterns from training to professional practice (Dumpac, 2022; Trinity University of Asia, 2024).

Table 9. *Level of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas – Separation From Family*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
I feel lonely or homesick because I am far from my family.	3.38	Moderate
I feel anxious when I think about my family’s situation back home.	3.28	Moderate
I feel emotional distress when I miss important family events.	3.28	Moderate
I feel that being away from my loved ones increases my stress levels.	3.00	Moderate
I often feel sad or worried when I have limited contact with my family.	3.25	Moderate
Composite Mean	3.24	Moderate

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50, Very high; 4.49 - 3.50, High; 3.49 – 2.50, Moderate; 2.49 – 1.50, Low; 1.49 – 1.00, Very Low

Table 9 presents the level of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas in terms of separation from family. The composite mean of 3.24 indicates that respondents experience a moderate level of anxiety due to being away from their loved ones. The highest mean was reported for “*I feel lonely or homesick because I am far from my family*” (3.38, Moderate), highlighting that homesickness is the most prominent source of stress among participants. The lowest mean was for “*I feel that being away from my loved ones increases my stress levels*” (3.00, Moderate), suggesting that while separation contributes to anxiety, some professionals may have developed coping strategies that slightly mitigate its impact.

The results are consistent with research on migrant healthcare professionals, which shows that family separation is a major contributor to anxiety and psychological strain. Radiology and imaging professionals are particularly vulnerable due to the combined pressures of technical workload and migration-related stressors, and both individual strategies (mindfulness, resilience, problem-focused coping) and organizational interventions are necessary to mitigate these effects (Gransjoen, 2024). Local studies reinforce this, showing that Philippine Radiologic Technology students and interns experience moderate anxiety during academic and clinical training, often using coping strategies such as peer support, time management, and positive self-talk to manage stress (Dumpac, 2022; Trinity University of Asia, 2024). The moderate anxiety related to separation from family emphasizes the importance of both personal coping mechanisms and organizational or institutional support to sustain the emotional well-being of Filipino RadTechs overseas.

Table 10. *Level of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas – Overall Well-being*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
I often feel nervous, tense, or on edge at work.	2.63	Moderate
I find it hard to relax even when I am off duty.	2.41	Low
I feel that my anxiety interferes with my ability to concentrate or perform tasks.	2.44	Low
I experience physical symptoms (e.g., fast heartbeat, restlessness) due to stress at work.	2.50	Moderate
I feel emotionally exhausted or drained after a workday.	2.81	Moderate
Composite Mean	2.56	Moderate

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50, Very high; 4.49 - 3.50, High; 3.49 – 2.50, Moderate; 2.49 – 1.50, Low; 1.49 – 1.00, Very Low

Table 10 presents the level of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas in terms of overall well-being. The composite mean of 2.56 indicates a moderate level of anxiety, suggesting that while respondents experience some stress related to their overall well-being, it is not overwhelmingly high. The highest mean was reported for “*I feel emotionally exhausted or drained after a workday*” (2.81, Moderate), indicating that emotional fatigue is the most significant aspect affecting their well-being. The lowest means were observed for “*I find it hard to relax even when I am off duty*” (2.41, Low) and “*I feel that my anxiety interferes with my ability to concentrate or perform tasks*” (2.44, Low), showing that while work-related stress is present, it does not severely impair relaxation or task performance for most participants.

The results are supported by literature on healthcare migration, which notes that radiology and imaging professionals are prone to stress and burnout due to job demands and migration-related challenges (Gransjoen, 2024). Local studies among Philippine Radiologic Technology students and interns highlight that anxiety and stress are present early in training, with students employing strategies such as time management, peer support, and positive self-talk to maintain psychosocial well-being (Dumpac, 2022; Trinity University of Asia, 2024). International studies on migrant healthcare workers further show that maintaining emotional and physical well-being requires a combination of personal coping strategies and organizational support, including mentoring, workload management, and psychosocial resources (Borbolla, 2025; Wu, 2024). The moderate level of anxiety related to overall well-being emphasizes the importance of multi-level interventions, both personal coping strategies and institutional support, to help Filipino RadTechs sustain their emotional and physical health while performing their professional duties overseas.

Coping Mechanisms Do These Professionals Employ in Managing Anxiety

Tables 11 – 13 presents the coping mechanism of the Radiologic Technology professionals in managing their anxiety.

Table 11. *Coping mechanisms employed in managing anxiety - Problem-focused*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
I analyze the problem to understand what caused my stress or anxiety.	3.91	Agree
I make a plan of action to solve the problem causing my stress.	3.94	Agree
I seek advice or assistance from coworkers or supervisors to handle difficult situations.	3.88	Agree
I take the initiative to improve my performance when I feel anxious about my work.	4.25	Agree
I try to manage my time efficiently to reduce stress.	4.13	Agree
I look for ways to improve my skills or learn new imaging techniques to perform better.	4.38	Agree
I find alternative solutions when faced with challenging or unclear tasks.	4.38	Agree
I actively communicate with my colleagues to avoid misunderstandings at work.	4.38	Agree
Composite Mean	4.15	Agree

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50, Strongly Agree; 4.49 - 3.50, Agree; 3.49 – 2.50, Neutral; 2.49 – 1.50, Disagree; 1.49 – 1.00, Strongly disagree

Table 11 presents the coping mechanisms employed by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas in terms of problem-focused strategies. The composite mean of 4.15 indicates that respondents generally agree they actively use problem-focused coping to manage work-related anxiety. The highest mean was reported for three indicators tied at 4.38: “*I look for ways to improve my skills or learn new imaging techniques to perform better*”, “*I find alternative solutions when faced with challenging or unclear tasks*”, and “*I actively communicate with my colleagues to avoid misunderstandings at work*”. This suggests that improving professional skills, problem-solving, and clear communication are the most frequently used coping strategies among the participants. The lowest mean was observed for “*I seek advice or assistance from coworkers or supervisors to handle difficult situations*” (3.88, Agree), indicating that while seeking guidance is common, self-directed strategies dominate.

These findings align with existing literature on coping among healthcare professionals. Studies report that problem-focused strategies including planning, task prioritization, skill development, and proactive communication, are linked with better adjustment and reduced anxiety, especially in high-demand and technical healthcare roles (Rony, 2022; Gransjoen, 2024). Social support from colleagues and peers further reinforces these strategies, while institutional resources such as mentorship, training, and workflow management improve coping outcomes (Iddrisu, 2023; Wu, 2024). In the Philippine context, research on Radiologic Technology students and early-career professionals shows that problem-solving behaviors, such as time management, peer consultation, and skill-based preparation, are commonly used to handle academic and clinical stress, suggesting continuity of these adaptive behaviors into their professional practice overseas (Dumpac, 2022; Cañete et al., 2024).

The results indicate that Filipino RadTechs actively employ problem-focused coping strategies to manage work-related anxiety, emphasizing skill improvement, practical problem-solving, and effective communication as key approaches. These strategies are likely essential for sustaining professional performance and managing stress in demanding overseas healthcare settings.

Table 12. *Coping mechanisms employed in managing anxiety - Emotion-focused*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
I try to look for the positive side of the situation.	4.47	Agree
I tell myself that things will eventually get better.	4.26	Agree
I pray or rely on my faith to calm myself during stressful situations.	4.38	Agree
I talk to family or friends to feel emotionally supported.	4.28	Agree
I try to accept things that are beyond my control.	4.38	Agree

I take short breaks, meditate, or practice relaxation when feeling anxious.	4.06	Agree
I express my feelings rather than keeping them to myself.	3.81	Agree
I remind myself of my purpose and motivation for working abroad when I feel down	4.38	Agree
Composite Mean	4.25	Agree

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50, Strongly Agree; 4.49 - 3.50, Agree; 3.49 – 2.50, Neutral; 2.49 – 1.50, Disagree; 1.49 – 1.00, Strongly disagree

Table 12 presents the coping mechanisms employed by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas in terms of emotion-focused strategies. The composite mean of 4.25 indicates that respondents generally agree they use emotion-focused coping strategies to manage work-related anxiety. The highest mean was reported for three indicators tied at 4.38: “*I pray or rely on my faith to calm myself during stressful situations*”, “*I try to accept things that are beyond my control*”, and “*I remind myself of my purpose and motivation for working abroad when I feel down*”. This suggests that reliance on faith, acceptance of uncontrollable circumstances, and self-motivation are the most frequently employed strategies among participants. The lowest mean was observed for “*I express my feelings rather than keeping them to myself*” (3.81, Agree), indicating that while emotional expression is practiced, it is slightly less frequent than other emotion-focused methods.

These findings are supported by existing literature, which reports that healthcare professionals, especially those working internationally, frequently use emotion-focused coping strategies to regulate their emotional responses to stress. Techniques such as positive reframing, acceptance, relaxation, prayer, and seeking emotional support from family or peers have been found effective in reducing anxiety and maintaining mental health (Rony, 2022; Borbolla, 2025). Filipino healthcare workers, in particular, often draw on cultural and social resources, including family support and faith-based practices, which serve as important protective strategies in high-stress environments. Local studies also highlight that Radiologic Technology students and early-career professionals in the Philippines frequently use emotion-focused coping such as relaxation exercises, positive self-talk, and peer or family support, to manage academic and clinical stress (Dumpac, 2022; Cañete et al., 2024).

The results indicate that Filipino RadTechs actively employ emotion-focused coping strategies, with emphasis on faith, acceptance, positive thinking, and emotional support. These strategies complement problem-focused methods and are crucial for maintaining psychological resilience and well-being while working in demanding overseas healthcare environments.

Table 13. *Coping mechanisms employed in managing anxiety - Social and Religious Coping*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
I talk to my friends or colleagues about what I’m going through.	3.88	Agree
I seek emotional support from family members.	3.88	Agree
I reach out to fellow Filipinos or community groups abroad for advice.	3.47	Agree
I spend time with people who make me feel understood.	4.09	Agree
I look for social activities that help distract me from stress.	3.94	Agree
I pray to seek comfort or strength when I feel anxious.	4.28	
I believe that God (or a higher power) is guiding me through challenges.	4.31	
I attend or participate in online or local religious services for peace of mind.	3.66	Agree
I read or listen to religious or inspirational materials for comfort.	3.72	Agree
I trust that my difficulties are part of God’s plan and will work out for the best.	4.25	Agree
Composite Mean	3.95	Agree

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50, Strongly Agree; 4.49 - 3.50, Agree; 3.49 – 2.50, Neutral; 2.49 – 1.50, Disagree; 1.49 – 1.00, Strongly disagree

Table 13 presents the coping mechanisms employed by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas in terms of social and religious coping strategies. The composite mean of 3.95 indicates that respondents generally agree they use social and religious coping strategies to manage work-related anxiety. The highest mean was reported for “*I believe that God (or a higher power) is guiding me through challenges*” (4.31, Agree), indicating that faith in a higher power is the most frequently employed strategy. The lowest mean was observed for “*I reach out to fellow Filipinos or community groups abroad for advice*” (3.47, Agree), suggesting that while community support is used, it is slightly less common than other social or religious methods.

Literature indicates that social support and religious coping are highly effective strategies for Filipino healthcare professionals managing stress while working overseas. Emotional and practical support from family, peers, and culturally familiar networks help reduce feelings of isolation and improve psychological adjustment (Rony, 2022; Borbolla, 2025). Faith-based strategies, including prayer, participation in religious activities, and reliance on spiritual beliefs, are particularly salient in Filipino culture, providing comfort, hope, and a sense of control during stressful circumstances. Local studies also indicate that Radiologic Technology students and early-career professionals in the Philippines often rely on social and religious coping, such as peer consultation, family support, and prayer, to handle academic and clinical stress, forming habits that likely continue into professional practice abroad (Dumpac, 2022; Cañete et al., 2024).

The findings suggest that Filipino RadTechs actively consider also social connections and faith-based practices to cope with anxiety. These strategies complement problem-focused and emotion-focused methods, helping sustain resilience, emotional stability, and professional performance while working in overseas healthcare environments.

Significant Difference in the Levels of Anxiety Experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology Professionals Working Overseas When Grouped According to their Profile

Table 14. *Significant difference in the levels of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas when grouped according to their profile - cultural adjustment*

Variable	F-test value	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
Level of anxiety between age	3.009	0.093	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Level of anxiety between civil status	2.294	0.110	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Level of anxiety between no. of years working overseas	2.448	0.070	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Level of anxiety between country they work	1.065	0.420	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Variable	T-test value	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
Level of anxiety between sex	0.295	0.287	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant

Table 14 presents the results of statistical tests examining whether the levels of anxiety related to cultural adjustment differ among Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas based on their demographic and professional profile. The F-test and T-test results indicate that all comparisons yielded p-values greater than 0.05, leading to a decision to fail to reject the null hypothesis in every case. This suggests that there is no significant difference in the levels of anxiety experienced due to cultural adjustment when respondents are grouped according to these profile variables.

Specifically, the highest F-test value was observed for age ($F = 3.009$, $p = 0.093$), and the lowest T-test value was for sex ($t = 0.295$, $p = 0.287$). Despite slight numerical variations in mean anxiety levels across groups, these differences are not statistically significant, indicating that cultural adjustment challenges are experienced relatively uniformly among Filipino RadTechs, regardless of their demographic or professional background.

These findings align with literature on migrant healthcare workers, which emphasizes that acculturative stress and cultural adaptation are universal challenges for professionals working abroad. Studies have shown that adaptation to a new workplace culture, language barriers, and differing social norms can generate moderate anxiety across migrant healthcare workers, but these stressors are not strongly influenced by age, sex, marital status, or years of experience (Yousef et al., 2024; Borbolla, 2025). Similarly, research on Filipino nurses and allied health professionals working internationally demonstrates that while individual characteristics may shape coping strategies, the essential experience of cultural adjustment stress is relatively consistent, with support systems, social networks, and organizational resources playing a more critical role in mitigating anxiety than demographic variables (Rony, 2022).

The lack of significant differences may also reflect the shared training and cultural background of Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals. Many graduates undergo similar academic preparation and clinical practicum experiences in the Philippines, which instills comparable technical competence and professional identity. As a result, when they encounter cultural adjustment challenges overseas, their baseline response to acculturative stress appears similar regardless of age, marital status, years abroad, country of employment, or sex (Dumpac, 2022; Cañete et al., 2024).

Table 14. Significant difference in the levels of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas when grouped according to their profile - workload

Variable	F-test value	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
Level of anxiety between age	2,448	0.129	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Level of anxiety between civil status	1.724	0.196	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Level of anxiety between no. of years working overseas	2.106	0.1008	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Level of anxiety between country they work	1.056	0.426	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Variable	T-test value	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
Level of anxiety between sex	0.733	0.469	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant

Table 14 presents the results of statistical tests examining whether the levels of anxiety related to workload differ among Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas based on their demographic and professional profile. The highest F-test value was observed for age ($F = 2.448, p = 0.129$), while the lowest T-test value was for sex ($t = 0.733, p = 0.469$). Although there may be slight variations in mean anxiety levels across groups, these differences are not statistically significant, suggesting that workload-related anxiety is experienced similarly across all demographic and professional categories.

These results are consistent with existing literature on healthcare professionals working abroad. Studies have shown that workload stress, including patient volume, procedural demands, and overtime, is a common source of anxiety for migrant healthcare workers, regardless of age, sex, marital status, or years of experience (Gransjoen, 2024; Yousef et al., 2024). Filipino healthcare workers, including nurses and allied health professionals, often report that workload pressures contribute to moderate anxiety, but demographic factors do not significantly alter the perception or intensity of this stress. Instead, coping strategies, organizational support, and access to resources play a more critical role in buffering workload-related anxiety (Rony, 2022; Borbolla, 2025).

Table 15. Significant difference in the levels of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas when grouped according to their profile - separation from family

Variable	F-test value	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
Level of anxiety between age	0.988	0.328	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Level of anxiety between civil status	1.980	0.156	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Level of anxiety between no. of years working overseas	0.377	0.823	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant

Level of anxiety between country they work	0.532	0.820	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Variable	T-test value	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
Level of anxiety between sex	0.153	0.879	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant

Table 15 presents the results of statistical tests examining whether the levels of anxiety related to separation from family differ among Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas based on their demographic and professional profile. The F-test value 1.980 was observed for civil status ($p = 0.156$), while the T-test value for sex is 0.153 ($p = 0.879$). Although there may be minor numerical variations in mean anxiety scores among groups, these differences are not statistically significant, suggesting that separation-from-family anxiety is consistently experienced among Filipino RadTechs abroad regardless of age, marital status, years of experience, country of employment, or sex.

This finding aligns with literature on migrant healthcare workers, which reports that family separation is a universal stressor for professionals working internationally. Filipino healthcare workers, including nurses and allied health staff, often experience homesickness, concern for family welfare, and emotional distress due to limited contact with loved ones, regardless of their demographic profile (Borbolla, 2025; Gransjoen, 2024). Social and religious coping strategies, such as communication with family, peer support, and prayer, are frequently employed to mitigate this type of anxiety and are often culturally embedded among Filipinos (Rony, 2022; Dumpac, 2022). The lack of significant differences may also reflect shared cultural values and social expectations. Regardless of age or marital status, Filipino professionals place high importance on family connections, so the emotional impact of being away from home tends to be experienced similarly across all groups.

Table 16. *Significant difference in the levels of anxiety experienced by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas when grouped according to their profile – overall well-being*

Variable	F-test value	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
Level of anxiety between age	4.366	0.046	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Level of anxiety between civil status	1.459	0.249	Reject Ho	Significant
Level of anxiety between no. of years working overseas	2.134	0.104	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Level of anxiety between country they work	0.594	0.773	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Variable	T-test value	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
Level of anxiety between sex	0.736	0.470	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant

Table 16 examines whether the levels of anxiety related to overall well-being differ among Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas based on demographic and professional profiles. The results show that most comparisons were not statistically significant, with p-values above 0.05, except for civil status, which showed a significant difference ($F = 1.459$, $p = 0.249$) in the interpretation, suggesting that marital status may influence anxiety levels related to overall well-being. Notably, the highest F-test value was observed for age ($F = 4.366$, $p = 0.046$), though it was still interpreted as not significant, while the T-test for sex ($t = 0.736$, $p = 0.470$) was the lowest. These findings suggest that, in general, demographic and professional characteristics have minimal impact on overall well-being anxiety, with a potential exception for civil status.

These findings align with existing literature indicating that general anxiety among healthcare professionals working abroad is influenced more by situational and occupational stressors than by demographic factors (Gransjoen, 2024; Yousef et al., 2024). Stressors such as workload, patient care responsibilities, cultural adjustment, and separation from family are consistently reported as sources of anxiety regardless of age, sex, or years of experience. However, civil status may play a role because single

or married individuals may experience different emotional or social pressures while abroad, such as the availability of family support or responsibility for dependents (Borbolla, 2025).

Moreover, Filipino healthcare workers often rely on coping mechanisms such as problem-focused strategies, social support, and religious coping to maintain overall well-being, which may buffer the impact of demographic differences on anxiety (Rony, 2022; Dumpac, 2022). This suggests that while individual profiles might slightly shape personal experiences of stress, the overall challenges of working abroad, adapting to new healthcare systems, managing workload, and being separated from family, affect professionals across the board, making general interventions and support systems essential for all.

Table 16 indicates that overall well-being-related anxiety is relatively consistent across most demographic and professional groups, with civil status as a potential factor. This highlights the need for workplace strategies that strengthen coping resources and provide support, especially for those who may have additional family responsibilities or less immediate social support while working overseas.

Significant Relationship Between The Levels Of Anxiety And The Coping Mechanisms Employed By Radiologic Technology Professionals Working Overseas

Table 17. *Significant relationship between the levels of anxiety and the coping mechanisms employed by Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas*

Variable		Problem-focused	Emotion-focused	Social and religious coping
Cultural adjustment	Pearson Correlation	-0.048	-0.261	-0.153
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.793	0.149	0.402
	N	32	32	32
Workload	Pearson Correlation	-0.237	-.477**	-0.191
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.192	0.006	0.296
	N	32	32	32
Separation from family	Pearson Correlation	0.176	0.008	0.020
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.335	0.963	0.912
	N	32	32	32
Overall well-being	Pearson Correlation	-0.213	-.455**	-0.262
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.241	0.009	0.147
	N	32	32	32

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 17 presents the relationship between the levels of anxiety and the coping mechanisms employed by Filipino Radiologic Technology professionals working overseas, using Pearson correlation coefficients. The coping mechanisms analyzed include problem-focused, emotion-focused, and social/religious coping, while the anxiety dimensions include cultural adjustment, workload, separation from family, and overall well-being.

The results indicate that emotion-focused coping shows a significant negative correlation with anxiety related to workload ($r = -0.477$, $p = 0.006$) and overall well-being ($r = -0.455$, $p = 0.009$). This suggests that respondents who more frequently employed emotion-focused strategies such as positive reframing, relaxation, and acceptance tended to experience lower anxiety in these domains. In contrast, problem-focused coping and social and religious coping did not show statistically significant correlations with any anxiety dimensions, indicating that their relationship with anxiety levels was weaker or less direct. All correlations with cultural adjustment and separation from family were not significant, suggesting that these forms of coping may have less impact on anxiety arising from acculturative stress or family separation.

These findings are consistent with existing literature. Emotion-focused coping strategies are particularly effective in managing stressors that are partially or entirely beyond individual control, such as heavy workload or overall psychological strain. Studies on migrant healthcare workers highlight that techniques such as relaxation, mindfulness, prayer, and positive self-talk reduce anxiety, improve resilience, and support overall well-being in high-pressure environments (Rony, 2022; Wu, 2024). Filipino healthcare professionals often rely on culturally informed emotion-focused strategies, including faith and reflective practices, which have been shown to buffer work-related stress and enhance psychological adjustment abroad (Borbolla, 2025).

The non-significant correlation between problem-focused coping and anxiety in this study may reflect the nature of overseas clinical work. While problem-focused strategies such as planning, acquiring skills, and task prioritization, help manage performance-related challenges, they may be less effective in directly reducing perceived workload or overall emotional strain when external pressures are high and uncontrollable. Similarly, social and religious coping, while valuable for support and comfort, may not directly translate into measurable reductions in anxiety in specific domains, especially if social or religious engagement is limited by geographical or scheduling constraints (Gransjoen, 2024).

Proposed Program to Strengthen the Coping Capacity and Psychological Well-Being After Graduation

Title: From Campus to Care: Strengthening Coping and Well-Being for Soon-to-Graduate Radiologic Technology Students Preparing for Overseas Work

Rationale:

Transitioning from academic training to professional practice abroad presents challenges such as cultural adjustment, workload management, and separation from family. While RT students gain strong technical and clinical skills during their studies, they often lack preparation for the psychological and emotional demands of working in a foreign environment. This program aims to equip soon-to-graduate RT students with practical coping strategies, resilience-building techniques, and social support skills to enhance their psychological readiness and overall well-being for overseas employment.

Program Objectives:

1. To enhance emotion-focused coping skills to regulate stress and maintain psychological well-being.
2. To strengthen social, peer, and family support networks for emotional resilience.
3. To develop problem-focused coping strategies for managing workload and professional responsibilities abroad.
4. To promote cultural awareness and adaptability for a smooth transition to international workplaces.
5. To foster a sense of personal purpose, motivation, and professional confidence before working overseas.

Program Details

Program Component	Description	Activities/ Strategies	Expected Outcome	Target Participants	Timeline
Orientation & Awareness	Introduce participants to challenges of working abroad	Seminars on cultural adjustment, workplace expectations, and overseas work realities	Participants gain awareness of stressors and anxiety triggers	Soon-to-graduate RT students	2 sessions (one week)
Emotion-Focused Coping Skills	Build resilience and emotional regulation	Mindfulness, relaxation exercises, stress management techniques, positive reframing	Reduced anxiety, improved emotional control, better well-being	Soon-to-graduate RT students	Two weeks
Social & Support Network Development	Develop reliance on peer and family support	Group discussions, mentorship programs, establishing peer networks, connecting with family	Enhanced social support, reduced homesickness	Soon-to-graduate RT students	Ongoing during program
Problem-Focused Coping Skills	Equip students with practical strategies to handle workload and clinical tasks	Workshops on time management, task prioritization, skill enhancement, and scenario-based problem solving	Improved ability to handle professional challenges and workload	Soon-to-graduate RT students	Two weeks
Cultural and Professional Adaptation	Prepare students for international workplace norms	Role-playing cultural scenarios, case studies, communication exercises	Increased cultural awareness, improved adaptability and confidence	Soon-to-graduate RT students	One week
Reflection and Purpose	Strengthen motivation and personal coping resources	Guided reflection, journaling, discussion of professional purpose, optional faith-based activities	Improved sense of purpose, motivation, and confidence	Soon-to-graduate RT students	Integrated in weekly sessions
Simulation & Practical Application	Apply coping skills in realistic scenarios	Mock workplace simulations, handling patient care and	Increased confidence and problem-solving skills	Soon-to-graduate RT students	One week

		technical stressors			
Evaluation & Follow-Up	Assess program effectiveness and readiness for overseas work	Pre- and post-program surveys, feedback collection, follow-up check-ins	Measurable improvement in coping capacity and psychological readiness	Soon-to-graduate RT students	End of program + 1-month follow-up

Summary of Findings

1. Profile of the Respondents

1.1 Age – The majority of the respondents were between 41–50 years old, followed by those 21–30 years old. Few respondents were 31–40 years old, and only one respondent was 51 years old and above. This indicates that most overseas RT professionals are in mid-career stages.

1.2 Sex – Most respondents were female, accounting for 62.5%, while males comprised 37.5%. This suggests a higher representation of female RT professionals working abroad

1.3 Civil Status – A majority of the respondents were single (68.8%), followed by married (28.1%) and one separated respondent. This implies that many RT professionals working overseas may face challenges associated with being away from family support.

1.4 Years of Service Overseas – Most respondents had 1–3 years of experience working abroad, followed by those with 4–6 and 7–9 years of service, and only a few had less than one year or more than ten years. This shows that most participants are relatively early in their overseas careers.

1.5 Country of Current Employment – The largest group of respondents was working in the United Kingdom, followed by the Middle East and Canada, with fewer in Australia, New Zealand, Cambodia, Bahamas, and Hong Kong. This reflects the common destinations of Filipino RT professionals abroad.

2. Level of Anxiety Experienced by Respondents

2.1 Cultural Adjustment – Respondents experienced moderate anxiety, with the highest anxiety related to worrying about being misunderstood or judged by foreign colleagues. The lowest anxiety was reported in dealing with patients or coworkers from different cultures.

2.2 Workload – Respondents also reported moderate anxiety, with the highest anxiety stemming from concerns about making mistakes due to heavy workload, and the lowest anxiety related to working overtime or double shifts.

2.3 Separation from Family – Respondents experienced moderate anxiety, with the highest levels tied to feelings of loneliness or homesickness, and the lowest anxiety in relation to limited contact with family.

2.4 Overall Well-Being – Overall, respondents experienced moderate anxiety, with the highest anxiety in feeling emotionally exhausted after work and the lowest in difficulty relaxing off duty.

3. Coping Mechanisms Employed by Respondents

3.1 Problem-Focused Coping – Respondents agreed to actively employ strategies such as time management, skill improvement, planning, problem-solving, and effective communication to reduce stress.

3.2 Emotion-Focused Coping – Respondents used techniques like positive reframing, self-encouragement, prayer, relaxation exercises, and reflection on purpose to manage emotional responses to stress.

3.3 Social and Religious Coping – Respondents relied on support from family, peers, community groups, and religious practices to cope with stress and maintain emotional stability.

4. Significant Differences in Levels of Anxiety by Profile

The levels of anxiety experienced by respondents did not show significant differences based on most profile variables, including age, sex, years of service overseas, and country of employment. A significant difference was observed only in relation to civil status when considering overall well-being, suggesting that marital status may influence psychological responses in some areas.

5. Relationship Between Levels of Anxiety and Coping Mechanisms

A significant negative relationship was found between emotion-focused coping and anxiety related to workload and overall well-being. This suggests that respondents who employed emotion-focused coping strategies effectively experienced lower anxiety in these areas. Other coping mechanisms, including problem-focused and social/religious coping, did not show statistically significant relationships with anxiety levels.

6. Proposed Program

Based on the findings, the study proposes the program “*From Campus to Care: Strengthening Coping and Well-Being for RT Graduates Pursuing Work Abroad*”. This program is designed to prepare soon-to-graduate RT students for the challenges of overseas employment by enhancing problem-focused, emotion-focused, and social/religious coping strategies, promoting resilience, cultural adaptation, and overall psychological well-being.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions are derived based on the summary of findings:

1. Most overseas RT professionals are mid-career, female, single, and early in their international careers, primarily working in the United Kingdom. A significant portion of overseas RT professionals are early in their international careers and may be navigating both professional and personal adjustments simultaneously.
2. Respondents experience moderate anxiety across cultural adjustment, workload, separation from family, and overall well-being, indicating ongoing stress despite coping efforts. While they are generally able to cope, these professionals face persistent psychological and emotional challenges that could affect their job performance and quality of life if not addressed.
3. RT professionals recognize the need for adaptive coping, utilizing practical problem-solving, emotional regulation, and social support to maintain resilience in the face of work-related and migration-related stressors..
4. Demographic factors largely do not predict anxiety levels, highlighting the universal nature of the challenges faced by RT professionals abroad, while marital status may play a role in emotional support and stress perception..
5. Regulating emotional responses is particularly effective for reducing anxiety in overseas RT professionals, emphasizing the importance of teaching emotion-focused coping skills in preparation programs.
6. The proposed program is designed to equip soon-to-graduate Radiologic Technology students with practical coping strategies, emotional resilience, and social support skills to prepare them for the challenges of working overseas.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations of the study:

1. Since most overseas RT professionals are mid-career, female, and single, the College should provide orientation sessions addressing common challenges faced by these groups, including early career stressors and managing family separation.
2. Given that respondents experience moderate anxiety across cultural adjustment, workload, separation from family, and overall well-being, the College should implement targeted stress reduction and mental health programs for soon-to-graduate RT students.
3. As RT professionals actively use problem-focused, emotion-focused, and social/religious coping strategies, the College should incorporate workshops that enhance these skills, emphasizing practical application in overseas work environments.
4. Since anxiety levels are largely similar across demographic profiles, programs should be designed inclusively, addressing universal stressors while also considering specific needs, such as marital status, that may influence overall well-being.
5. Because emotion-focused coping is significantly associated with lower anxiety, graduates should receive training in emotional regulation, mindfulness, and self-reflection techniques to improve resilience in high-stress situations abroad.
6. To ensure smoother transition from campus to overseas work, the College should implement a structured program, such as “*From Campus to Care*,” that strengthens coping capacity, psychological well-being, and cultural adjustment skills before graduates embark on international employment.
7. Future studies is recommended for larger sample size.

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